

Dates
 2019 34

Survey
 20280 26
 614261 5
 533486 2
 533482 1

Altitude (m)
 0.0--100.0 26
 500.0

Results
 34 datasets found Transfer Datasets

[998a770a_f4bf4345-a043-4830-bd0a-59ee9ebe371e.jpg](#)

Year	Altitude (m)	GPS Location	Survey
2019	17.651	26.10719914, -81.76483583	20280

[9c3063e5_b488cf80-fcf4-4304-aa84-63a5a6d2dc49.jpg](#)

Year	Altitude (m)	GPS Location	Survey

[← Back to Search](#)

Filename: 9c3063e5_b488cf80-fcf4-4304-aa84-63a5a6d2dc49.jpg

Transfer/Sync Download via HTTPS Get link Run Compute Flow

General Info

You invoked a flow to process file 9c3063e5_b488cf80-fcf4-4304-aa84-63a5a6d2dc49.jpg

[Manage the flow run](#) in the Globus web app.

 When the flow completes, [click here to view analysis results](#) in the shared repository.

Globus Science Gateway Portal

- Browse datasets via Globus Search
- **Discover**, select data of interest
- **Analyze** selected data using Globus Compute
- **Export, move, share** analysis results via Globus Transfer
- **Scale** with Globus Flows
- **Enable** broad access
 - Federated login and access control via Globus Auth
 - Extensible, Django-based framework
 - Template-driven search results and landing pages

<https://github.com/globus/django-globus-portal-framework>

<https://sgportal.globusdemo.org>